
GAPMINDER ARTIFICIAL IGNORANCE BENCHMARK

A PREPRINT

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ABSTRACT

We tested the knowledge about world facts amongst AIs. In Oct 2023 and Jan 2024, we carried out an experiment which assessed the performance of 10 Large Language Models (LLMs) with 278 world fact questions. The results indicate that, on average, AIs outperform individual monkeys and humans. However, they still do not answer all questions correctly, which means that AIs are skewed by misconceptions as well. Based on this experiment, we consider a dataset and a benchmark for world fact questions important for a factual AI, and we aim to develop such a dataset and benchmark to help fight the ignorance in AIs!

Keywords Artificial Intelligence, Large Language Models, Ignorance, Benchmark

1 Motivation

The recent advancements in Large Language Models (LLMs) have greatly increased AI's capabilities across various tasks. Considering the rising usage of LLMs in search engines (such as Bing) and learning platforms (such as Khan Academy), we are interested in finding out whether these models, like humans, might also have misconceptions. To explore this, we have initiated an experiment to test LLMs using a set of fact questions that have been posed to humans as well. The objective of these experiments is to establish a benchmark that effectively assesses the knowledge of LLMs. Through the creation of such a benchmark, our aim is to provide a reliable method for evaluating the accuracy and reliability of LLMs. By ensuring the accuracy and reliability of LLMs, we can then confidently employ them in applications, especially those applications for assisting the education about humanity, about our living environment and economics.

2 Questions to answer

We had following questions in mind when we started the experiment:

1. Does the answer vary if we ask the same question multiple times?
2. Does the answer vary by the model configurations such as variations in temperature?
3. Does the answer vary with the framing of the question?
4. Does the answer vary by model?

More details about the original questions can be found in our initial experiment document.

3 Methodology

3.1 The Dataset

The questions dataset in our experiment were extracted from our Worldview Upgrader service. In the Worldview Upgrader, we have over 1,500 fact questions covering many topics. In our experiment, we currently use 278 questions

related to the SDGs and global issues. We also translated the questions into Chinese so that we can test Chinese chatbots. Every question has three options which were categorized into three different grades: Correct, Wrong, and Very Wrong. (For more details, see: the current question set)

3.2 Prompt variations and model variations

To find out if a model responds differently to how we ask a question, we designed many variations of “prompt template” which are templates for building up inputs to the model. We feed question data to a prompt template to create the actual input (prompt) that will be sent to the model.

To begin with, we tested following 3 prompts:

1. Please answer this multiple choices question. If you can't determine the answer please make your best guess:

Question:
{question_text}
A. {option_a}
B. {option_b}
C. {option_c}

Answer:

2. Question:
{question_text}
Is it: {option_a}; {option_b}; or {option_c}?

Answer:

3. Pick the correct answer: A, B or C. If you can't determine the answer please make your best guess.

Question:
{question_text}
A. {option_a}
B. {option_b}
C. {option_c}

Answer:

The first prompt is designed to simulate answering questions in Worldview Upgrader, while the second prompt uses more natural language and does not ask the LLM to choose between A, B or C. The third prompt was added in the 2024-01-29 update, to make it clearer to the LLMs that we are interested in an answer A, B or C (we added this prompt because we observed many answers from the LLMs did not choose one of the listed options, but just answered the question free form instead).

Note that, we didn't set the “system prompt” in all models so they are using the model defaults. We also included a Chinese version of these prompts when testing questions in Chinese.

[Link to current prompt variations set](#)

To find out whether model configurations, such as variations in temperature (a parameter that controls the randomness of the language model's output) will influence the responses of a model, we included different parameters for the same model in the experiment.

On the other hand, LLMs generate text based on probabilistic patterns learned from vast amounts of training data. While the same prompt and low temperature setting can guide the output towards certain directions, the inherent randomness in the model can lead to divergent outputs. This led us to test models with the same settings multiple times, to see if they score differently.

[Link to current model variations set](#)

3.3 Evaluation process

We are using Yival as our evaluation framework. It will first calculate all combinations of questions, model configuration variations and prompt variations and then send requests based on each combination and gather outputs. After that, it will evaluate each output and calculate scores for predetermined metrics.

Notes:

- We only evaluate final output from models, and will not check the probability of all available options like some other benchmarks do.
- We tested Alibaba’s model with Chinese questions only, and tested other models with English questions only.

3.3.1 Evaluation Metrics

We adopt the G-Eval method in our evaluation process, which means that we use gpt-4 to help evaluate the outputs. Currently only correctness is evaluated, but we plan to add more metrics in the future.

Link to prompts used for evaluation of correctness

We also calculate a final score per model and prompt combination. To calculate the final result scores we follow these steps:

1. We have asked the model (with a specific configuration) 5 times for each prompt. To control for variations in answers across these repetitions, we use these definitions:
 - A) Definition of **correct answer**
 - The most frequently given answer by the model matches the correct answer.
 - B) Definition of **wrong answer**
 - The most frequently given answer by the model matches the wrong answer.
 - C) Definition of **very wrong answer**
 - The most frequently given answer by the model matches the very wrong answer.
 - D) Definition of **indecisive answer**
 - If two answers are equally common or the most common answer is something like "I couldn't answer the question," we consider the model to be indecisive about the answer.
2. Next, we calculate:
 - A) **Correct Answer Rate %**:
 - $\text{Correctly answered questions} / \text{total questions} \times 100$
 - B) **Wrong Answer Rate %**:
 - $\text{Wrongly answered questions} / \text{total questions} \times 100$
 - C) **Very Wrong Answer Rate %**:
 - $\text{Very wrongly answered questions} / \text{total questions} \times 100$
 - D) **Indecisive Answer Rate %**:
 - $\text{Indecisively answered questions} / \text{total questions} \times 100$

To get a score for a particular model, we used the score for the best performing prompt for that model. Full results are available in the appendix.

All source code we used to run the experiment can be assessed in this github repo.

4 Results

Our experiments revealed that the variability of replies from LLMs is influenced by a few factors: the model, the model configuration, and the question framing. We will discuss each factor in sections below.

4.1 Does the answer vary if we ask the same question multiple times?

Yes. Our experiment shows that there is some level of variability of replies in all models tested. Table 1 shows a selection of the tested models with the average number of different answer categories (Correct, Wrong, Very Wrong or Indecisive) per question across 5 repeated rounds of identical questioning, where 1 means that all answers are the same. All models are using temperature = 0.01.

Model	Prompt	Average Number of Different Answer Categories
Google Gemini Pro (v1.0)	prompt1	1.02
	prompt2	1.00
	prompt3	1.02
OpenAI GPT 4 Turbo (gpt-4-0125-preview)	prompt1	1.06
	prompt2	1.06
	prompt3	1.05
OpenAI GPT 4 (gpt-4-0613)	prompt1	2.00
	prompt2	1.50
	prompt3	1.00
OpenAI GPT 3.5 Turbo (gpt-3.5-turbo-1106)	prompt1	1.09
	prompt2	1.12
	prompt3	1.13
Alibaba Qianwen Max (qwen-max-1201)	prompt1	1.42
	prompt2	1.65
	prompt3	1.44
Meta Llama 2	prompt1	1.08
	prompt2	1.06
	prompt3	1.00

Table 1: Average Number of Different Answer Categories by Model and Prompt

4.2 Does the answer vary by the model configurations such as variations in temperature?

Yes. We tested the GPT 3.5 turbo model with different “temperature” settings. Temperature setting is a parameter that controls the randomness of the generated text. Higher temperature values lead to more diverse and unpredictable responses, while lower values result in more focused and deterministic replies. From Table 2, we can see the correct rate dropped when using a higher temperature (1 instead of 0.01).

Model	Prompt	Correct %	Wrong %	Very Wrong %	Indecisive %
OpenAI GPT3.5 June 2023 {`temperature`: 0.01}	prompt1	38.9%	45.8%	15.3%	0.0%
	prompt2	67.9%	14.5%	11.1%	6.5%
OpenAI GPT3.5 June 2023 {`temperature`: 1}	prompt1	34.7%	41.6%	17.2%	6.5%
	prompt2	61.1%	13.7%	9.9%	15.3%

Table 2: Difference in results between GPT 3.5 Turbo 0.01 and 1.0 in temperature

4.3 Does the answer vary by model?

Yes. See Table 3.

Model	Correct %	Wrong %	Very Wrong %	Indecisive %
OpenAI GPT4 Turbo Jan 2024 {"temperature": 0.01}	84.3%	13.2%	2.1%	0.4%
OpenAI GPT4 Turbo Nov 2023 {"temperature": 0.01}	82.5%	12.5%	2.5%	2.5%
OpenAI GPT3.5 June 2023 {"temperature": 0.01}	67.9%	14.5%	11.1%	6.5%
OpenAI GPT3.5 Nov 2023 {"temperature": 0.01}	65.0%	25.0%	8.9%	1.1%
Alibaba Qianwen Max {"temperature": 0.01}	65.0%	17.9%	3.6%	13.6%
Google Gemini Pro {"temperature": 0.01}	63.9%	26.1%	9.6%	0.4%
OpenAI GPT4 June 2023 {"temperature": 0.01}	63.4%	15.3%	0.8%	20.6%
OpenAI GPT3.5 June 2023 {"temperature": 1}	61.1%	13.7%	9.9%	15.3%
Meta Llama 2 {"temperature": 0.01}	50.2%	36.8%	10.0%	3.1%
Alibaba Qianwen Plus* {"top_p": 0.1, "top_k": 100}	40.4%	21.2%	13.5%	25.0%
Google PaLM (Text Bison) {"temperature": 0.01}	36.3%	42.1%	14.7%	6.9%

Table 3: Correct Rates for the best performing prompt for each model

*Alibaba qwen-plus doesn't support temperature setting as the time we ran the experiment. So we use top_p and top_k to simulate the temperature setting.

4.4 Does the answer vary with the framing of the question?

Yes. Table 4 shows the choice of prompt significantly impacts the output of the model, e.g. gpt-3.5 doubling its performance with prompt2. LLMs seem to prefer natural language framing over multiple-choice framing. Caveat: prompt3 was introduced in the Jan 2024 experiment, and we didn't test all models with it.

Prompt	Correct Answer Rate
prompt1	63%
prompt2	72%
prompt3	60%

Table 4: Correct Rates break down by prompts

4.5 Discussion

4.5.1 Some observations

- To make sure the answer by an AI is good, we should ask the question a few times. Using a well tested prompt template to frame our questions also helps.
- GPT-4 performs better compared to other models in terms of correctness. And recent updates (the GPT-4 Turbo, 20231106 version and 20240125 version) also showed an improvement in correctness.
- Even the best performing models struggle with unanswered or incorrectly answered questions.
- Upon manual inspection of some of the answers and how GPT-4 evaluated the correctness of the answers, we find that the free-form prompt (prompt 2) more than other prompts results in long-winded answers that GPT-4 deems "Indecisive" even though the long-winded answer is more or less correct.

4.5.2 Conclusions

By random, a monkey scores 33% on an ABC question. Humans, on the other hand, score worse on many important fact questions about global development as our worldview is skewed by misconceptions. Based on the experiment, we can conclude that all tested Language Models are better than monkeys and humans on these questions (range 36% - 84% for the best performing prompt), but on the other hand, they did not achieve a perfect score for questions related to important world facts. Therefore, it is necessary to have a dataset and benchmark about world facts to train and test Language Models. We hope to develop such a dataset and benchmark to help fight the ignorance in AIs!

5 Ideas for future work

Try more models

- Google's most powerful model (Gemini Ultra) was not available at the time of running this experiment. It's worth testing it once it is available
- While we included LLama 2 70B in our Oct 2023 run, we have since seen many new open source LLMs released that are worth testing

Expand the dataset

- Incorporate country-specific questions and more languages into our dataset
- Create a private testing set, to avoid published questions becoming the training data for chatbots.

Prompt Variants

- Include more prompts / question framings variants
- See if the correctness evaluation can be improved using other prompts / models

Metrics

- Add more metrics. One important metric is consistency, which includes 2 parts:

- Consistency of the answer and the explanation to the answer
- Consistency of answers when asked several times and with different prompts
 - * For example, after receiving an answer, ask the model “Are you sure?”

Costs

- Using GPT 4 Turbo instead of GPT 4 in correctness-evaluation will make the cost of running the experiments lower

6 Appendix

6.1 Correct Rates by model configuration and prompt

Model	Prompt	Correct %	Wrong %	Very Wrong %	Indecisive %
OpenAI GPT4 Turbo Nov 2023 {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt1	78.6%	18.2%	2.5%	0.7%
OpenAI GPT4 Turbo Nov 2023 {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt2	82.5%	12.5%	2.5%	2.5%
OpenAI GPT4 Turbo Nov 2023 {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt3	76.4%	21.1%	2.5%	0.0%
OpenAI GPT4 Turbo Jan 2024 {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt1	79.6%	16.8%	3.6%	0.0%
OpenAI GPT4 Turbo Jan 2024 {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt2	84.3%	13.2%	2.1%	0.4%
OpenAI GPT4 Turbo Jan 2024 {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt3	74.3%	23.6%	2.1%	0.0%
OpenAI GPT4 June 2023 {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt1	59.2%	27.1%	2.3%	11.5%
OpenAI GPT4 June 2023 {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt2	63.4%	15.3%	0.8%	20.6%
OpenAI GPT3.5 Nov 2023 {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt2	65.0%	25.0%	8.9%	1.1%
OpenAI GPT3.5 Nov 2023 {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt1	37.1%	48.2%	14.3%	0.4%
OpenAI GPT3.5 Nov 2023 {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt3	35.0%	50.0%	15.0%	0.0%
OpenAI GPT3.5 June 2023 {"temperature": 1}	prompt1	34.7%	41.6%	17.2%	6.5%
OpenAI GPT3.5 June 2023 {"temperature": 1}	prompt2	61.1%	13.7%	9.9%	15.3%
OpenAI GPT3.5 June 2023 {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt1	38.9%	45.8%	15.3%	0.0%
OpenAI GPT3.5 June 2023 {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt2	67.9%	14.5%	11.1%	6.5%
Meta llama2* {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt1	31.8%	50.2%	16.1%	1.9%
Meta llama2* {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt2	50.2%	36.8%	10.0%	3.1%
Google PaLM (Text Bison) {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt1	39.0%	27.8%	22.4%	10.8%
Google PaLM (Text Bison) {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt2	36.3%	42.1%	14.7%	6.9%
Google Gemini Pro {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt1	53.6%	37.9%	8.6%	0.0%
Google Gemini Pro {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt2	63.9%	26.1%	9.6%	0.4%
Google Gemini Pro {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt3	50.4%	39.6%	10.0%	0.0%
Alibaba Qianwen Plus {"top_p": 0.1, "top_k": 100}	prompt1	36.5%	32.2%	12.0%	19.2%
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Alibaba Qianwen Max {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt1	64.6%	15.7%	8.9%	10.7%
Alibaba Qianwen Max {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt2	65.0%	17.9%	3.6%	13.6%
Alibaba Qianwen Max {"temperature": 0.01}	prompt3	62.1%	21.4%	8.9%	7.5%

*We tested the llama2 model hosted on Replicate

6.2 Full Results

Full Results can be accessed via this [Google Spreadsheet](#).